

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

EVALUATION OF JUVENILE DELINQUENCY RECIDIVISM SITUATION OF A SAMPLE DEVELOPING COUNTRY

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Abstract

Young people are the future of any society or nation. They are the ones who are going to take the nation forward. Honest, healthy, well educated, resourceful, and hard working balanced young work force is a valuable resource for any nation or country. It is the biggest resource for any nation. A nation can build its self up if they have young and hard working work force. Young people are the dreamers and future assets. Their dreams about a nation can become a reality if they are given the proper tools and care. Therefore, it is the duty of the nation is not let such a valuable resource go to waste. There are young offenders or as they are referred to as “juvenile delinquents” and they will exist as usual. In teenage we go through our rebellious phase as both our emotions and our body is growing. But that doesn’t mean that young offenders are going to be criminals for their entire lives by anyway. There should be better ways to deal with their delinquent behaviors. People can change and young people can definitely change as their ideals and morals are not yet set in stone. Giving up on them would mean to give up on a nation’s future. In a world of increasing violence and conflict, young people must be our strongest partners if peace and security are to win out over war. This paper will evaluate the preliminary statistics of young offenders, the reasons of repeatedly commit crime of young people, how other nations deal with it, how different criminal justice system addresses this problem and what’s the best possible solution for a sample developing country.

Keywords: juvenile delinquents, recidivism rate, criminal justice system, prison, prisoners

Introduction

Crime is an illegal act of gross violation of law for which someone may be punished by the government.¹⁴ Criminal is a very well known term to define a person who has committed a crime and has been legally convicted of a crime.¹⁵ Again, juvenile Delinquency is crime which is committed by young people.¹⁶ On the other hand, developing countries usually consider to nations characterized by a low standard of living, poor infrastructure, and a lack of industrialization.¹⁷ Sometime those countries are also refers to less-developed countries, third world countries, or even non-industrialized countries. A developing country, also known as emerging or transitional economy and which is *a nation with an underdeveloped industrial base*, and low Human Development Index (HDI).¹⁸ In this article I shall consider Bangladesh as sample developing country. All the statistics related to the topic considered on this article has been collected from print and electronic media, as well as on line data and

available information from other primary and secondary means. And the evaluation and analysis has been done on the basis of literatures, publications, doctrine and roles of necessity.

As we know that, people who commit crimes are sentenced for their actions by the Courts. In 2018 out of every 100,00 person living in Bangladesh 51.6 person are imprisoned.¹⁹ This would mean that, if there were 161.36 Million people living in Bangladesh in 2018,²⁰ where would be around 84,947 people in jail in total. That would mean that 0.52% of the population is confined in jail and which is all most close to the factual number found in 2018.²¹ On top of these statistics there are concerns about how many people are in jail pre-trial and how many of them are in actual prison after they are sentenced. The research shows that out of every 10 prisoners there are 8 of who are in jail in pre-trial for

¹⁴ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/crime>, accessed on 01 Aug 2024

¹⁵ <https://www.law.cornell.edu/wex/criminal>, accessed on 01 Aug 2024

¹⁶ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/juvenile-delinquency>, accessed on 01 Aug 2024

¹⁷ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/B9780080449104001024>, accessed on 01 Aug 2024

¹⁸ <https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/developing-countries/7401>, accessed on 01 Aug 2024

¹⁹ Statista (2023) Prison population rates in Bangladesh from 2008 to 2018, Feb 1, Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/699719/prison-population-rates-bangladesh/>, accessed on 8 March 2024

²⁰ Statista (2023) Bangladesh: Total population from 2018 to 2028. Oct 13. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/438167/total-population-of-bangladesh/>, accessed on 8 March 2024

²¹ World Prison Brief data (no date) World Prison Brief data Bangladesh, available at: <https://www.prisonstudies.org/country/bangladesh>, accessed on 8 March 2024

various reasons.²² The number of pre-trial detainees amount to 75.6% out of the total population in prison putting it at 61,367 in 2022.²³

The numbers of the juvenile criminals in cell in Bangladesh are also freighting as well. According to a research 0.7% of the total prison population of 68,700 in 2012 was made up of young people or minors.²⁴ This would mean that around 480 young people and minors were prison in 2012. Most of these crimes might be related to drug abuse. In the first half of 2020 1,191 young people were arrested in 821 cases throughout the nation.²⁵ There were 88,084 people in jail in 2020.²⁶ So that would mean that there has been an increase of 28.21% in overall jail population from 2012 to 2020. If we expect the juvenile population to be the same percentage as 2012 then, would have 616 juvenile delinquents in jail in 2020. That would mean that there would be a 22% increase in young people being behind bars. This calculation doesn't take any of the other real life factors into account and this could very well be a low estimate. This is an analytical paper which will collect, analyze and evaluate the preliminary statistics of young offenders, the reasons of repeatedly commit crime of young people, dealing of other nations related such crime, diversified criminal justice system relevant to this problem and the recommended best possible solution for a sample developing country like Bangladesh.

National Price Hike in the Horizon

We are living in a complex and frequent changing globe in the universe. Here, young people's economical, social, environmental and political atmospheric is changes over time. Ever changing factors like inflation going higher making less things affordable for people as a result of which these young people are not getting enough economic opportunities to express or discover themselves. It seems that, compared to last year's end to 2024's January prices increased for very common things like food, cloths, housing and utilities and transportation.²⁷ This increases the economic burden on the young people which might lead to higher crime rates.

In Bangladesh the price of the land for housing in the capital city of Dhaka in 2022 has reportedly been on the rise, from Tk 25 lakh to Tk 52 lakh per katha for

luxurious housing in the suburbs, while an average square feet price rose from Tk 5,000 to Tk 7,000 for an apartment in affordable areas.²⁸ These conditions are making it harder for younger people to afford a house and bear the cost of having a family. This has depressed young people to start their family life pushing the men to work harder to earn money to get married and start family life much later as well. This problem seems to only become much worse over coming time as, demand for urban housing is estimated to be around 6 million units in 2022, while the number expected to rise up to 10.5 million units by 2030.²⁹

The students housing at such ever-increasing rate has become a massive problem. It is understandable that young would want get the best education since they have to compete with many more graduates and the job market becoming much more competitive and shrinking continuously. The cost of the valued private education in both high school and university is also out of reach of middle class family. For most students in Bangladesh, a monthly budget around TK 40,000 can provide them with a relatively comfortable living and that is not affordable for most of the student.³⁰

The medical expenses are ever increasing and health-care is becoming a challenge for general mass. In Bangladesh there are public healthcare programs along with private health insurance programs to help people to deal with the medical expenses. However this seems to be not enough as people's Out Of Pocket Expenditure (OOP) has been on the rise. An Out of Pocket Expenditure (medical) is the cost that one has to bare for themselves after government and/or insurance program has covered part of it. This can include pills, bills, the service, operation, care, doctor's visit among many other things along with general monthly expenditure.

International Price Hike in the Horizon

Global climate change challenges and the pandemic like COVID-19 have been disrupted food and energy production and distribution, pouring up costs for general mass around the globe. Russia's invasion of Ukraine has deteriorated for many member countries, an already difficult situation by raising the prices of energy, food, and fertilizers even higher and exacerbating energy and food scarcity.³¹ However,

²² Dhaka tribute (2021) What is causing prison overcrowding in Bangladesh? 9 Apr 2021, available at: <https://www.dhakatribune.com/bangladesh/243547/what-is-causing-prison-overcrowding-in-bangladesh>, accessed on 8 March 2024

²³ Opcit, World Prison Brief data, accessed on 8 March 2024

²⁴ Opcit, World Prison Brief data, accessed on 8 March 2024

²⁵ Prothomalo (2020), No attention given to alarming rise in juvenile crime, 17 November 2020, available at:

<https://en.prothomalo.com/bangladesh/crime-and-law/no-attention-given-to-alarming-rise-in-juvenile-crime>, accessed on 16 March 2024

²⁶ Opcit, World Prison Brief data, accessed on 8 March 2024

²⁷ Trading Economics (no date). Bangladesh Inflation Rate at 3-Month High, available at: <https://tradingeconomics.com/bangladesh/inflation-cpi#:~:text=3%2DMonth%20High->

[Bangladesh's%20annual%20inflation%20rate%20rose%20o%209.86%25%20in%20January%202024,\(6.92%25%20vs%206%25](https://tradingeconomics.com/bangladesh/inflation-cpi#:~:text=3%2DMonth%20High-), accessed on 16 March 2024

²⁸ Dream world Group BD, HOUSING MARKET of BANGLADESH IN year 2022, available at: <https://dreamworldgroupbd.com/housing-market-of-bangladesh-in-year-2022/#:~:text=Changes%20in%20home%20prices%20and,s>

[uch%20as%20Mirpur%2C%20Aftabnagar%2C%20and,](https://dreamworldgroupbd.com/housing-market-of-bangladesh-in-year-2022/#:~:text=Changes%20in%20home%20prices%20and,s) accessed on 31 March 2024

²⁹ Ibid

³⁰ Study in Bangladesh (no date). Education and Living Cost, available at:

https://www.studyinbangladesh.com.bd/education_living_cost#:~:text=For%20most%20students%2C%20a%20monthly,relatively%20comfortable%20living%20in%20Bangladesh.&text=Your%20food%20and%20housekeeping%20expenses,for%20three%20meals%20per%20day, accessed on 31 March 2024

³¹ <https://www.rescue.org/article/what-cost-living-crisis-looks-around-world>, accessed on 01 Aug 2024

global food and energy prices have fallen from their peak levels in mid-2022 and at the same time domestic prices and the risks to food production remain elevated in many economies, which hurting mostly poorer households. Although inflation has been declining in response to many central banks' interest rate hikes, most countries still face elevated headline and core inflation.³² The IMF has approved new upper-credit-tranche-quality arrangements or augmentations of those that already exist for eight countries facing acute

food insecurity since May 2022. Seven countries have benefited from new IMF programs mainly in Bangladesh, Benin, Cabo Verde, Mauritania, Mozambique, Sri Lanka, and Zambia, as well as Kenya's program has been augmented. The programs help countries address a broad range of balance of payments needs while strengthening social safety nets, including policies to help address the impact of the food crisis.³³

Figure 1: Food prices remain elevated even after taking all possible measures³⁴

War has been on the rise since about 2012 in Libya, Syria and Yemen, triggered by the 2011 Arab uprisings, after a decline in the 1990s and early 2000s. A fresh wave of major combat and conflict prompted by the Myanmar army's 2021 power grab and Russia's 2022 assault on Ukraine. Add to those 2023's devastation in Sudan and Gaza. Around the globe, more people are dying in fighting, being forced from their homes or in need of life-saving aid than in decades in this century.³⁵ The global economic, political and social situations are shifting towards the worst. Today there are more than 110 armed conflicts ongoing and some of these have lasted more than 50 years.³⁶ Some of these wars have disrupted global supply chain and started up new economic challenges for others elsewhere. The

Ukraine Russia war is leading to many current problems in the global food and oil supply chain issues. Many ships felled with wheat and corn have been left stranding at Ukrainian ports, as the ongoing Russia-Ukraine war drags on and restricts shipping in the Black Sea.³⁷ Now the global economic growth will proceed at a moderate pace. Future economic performance will vary across all important sectors and various regions, with Europe and the Americas experiencing lethargic growth and parts of Asia-Pacific and Africa achieving strong growth.³⁸ This has led to food shortages and inflation around the world. However, the real GDP growth in percentage around the globe has been shown in figure 2 below.

³² <https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/ar/2023/in-focus/cost-of-living-crisis/>, accessed on 01 Aug 2024

³³ <https://www.imf.org/en/Blogs/Articles/2022/09/26/africa-food-prices-are-soaring-amid-high-import-reliance>, accessed on 01 Aug 2024

³⁴ <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WEO/Issues/2023/04/11/world-economic-outlook-april-2023>, accessed on 02 Aug 2024

³⁵ <https://www.crisisgroup.org/global/10-conflicts-watch-2024>, accessed on 02 Aug 2024

³⁶ Geneva-Academy (not date). TODAY'S ARMED CONFLICTS. Available at:

<https://geneva-academy.ch/galleries/today-s-armed-conflicts>, accessed on 5 March 2024

³⁷KPMG, Immediate and long-term impacts of the Russia-Ukraine war on supply chain, available at: <https://kpmg.com/us/en/articles/2022/impacts-russia-ukraine-war-supply-chains.html#:~:text=Supply%20chain%20snarls%20and%20rising%20prices&text=Hundreds%20of%20ships%20laden%20with,and%20inflation%20around%20the%20world>, accessed on 5 March 2024

³⁸ <https://www.euromonitor.com/article/global-inflation-tracker-q4-2023-inflation-eases-despite-high-economic-uncertainty>, accessed on 02 Aug 2024

A quick look at the numbers: Real GDP growth (% change)

Figure 2: Real GDP growth in percentage around the globe and forecasted up to 2027³⁹

Another point of global supply chain issue that is rising is in the South China Sea. One of the world's most valuable commodities in the modern world is semiconductor. It is used to control the flow of electricity devices,⁴⁰ being used to make things ranging from computers, gaming consoles, etc. Taiwan is currently the undisputed leader when it comes to semiconductor manufacturing.⁴¹ Currently China and Taiwan is at odds with each other with other nations being involved in the matter including the USA. This could be a potential place for trade being disturbed. **Since the UN was founded 75 years ago, the nature of conflict and violence has been transformed significantly.**⁴² **Violent and conflicts are now tend to be less fatal and often waged between domestic groups rather than states. Homicides are becoming more frequent in some parts of the world. However, gender-based attacks are rising globally. The long-term impact on development of inter-personal violence, including aggression against children, is also more broadly documented. In addition, technological advances have raised concerns about lethal autonomous weapons and cyberattacks, the weaponization of bots and drones, and the live-streaming of radical assaults. There has also been an increase in criminal activity involving data hacks and ransomware.**⁴³ Today, new, further complex and additional sophisticated threats require imaginative and bold responses, and strengthened collaboration between

states, nations along with the private sector and civil society as a whole.⁴⁴

Recidivism and Its Consequences

The word "Recidivism" means the continuation of criminal behavior after they have been sentenced or adjudicated for it before in the past.⁴⁵ It is a behavioral pattern of criminal nature and which is the relapse back into old behavior of criminal nature. It is a cycle of committing crime, having being sentenced for said crime and once going out of jail they commit crimes again, thus the cycle starts a new once more. It's a loop of 'doing crime' then 'doing the time' then 'doing crime' again. Recidivism rate is calculated usually as from the time they are released from jail there they spend their time outside before which they are eventually put back into prison again for re-offending. This time frame can be from somewhere from 3 year to 5 years. It is one of the contributing factors for the high crime rate in Bangladesh. How can we reduce crime where we cannot stop people from re-offending? Each year new criminals are committing crimes at the same time the old offenders are continuing their old criminal habits.

Actually, there are concerns about people who commit crimes when they are out in bail. Recently in an abduction and ransom case in Bangladesh, 2 criminals out of 5, namely Abdul Malek and Roni Nabal were re-offenders.⁴⁶ Abdul Malek was in bail while he did the abduction said news media.⁴⁷ In

³⁹ <https://www.spglobal.com/marketintelligence/en/mi/research-analysis/global-economy-growing-moderate-pace-inflation-subside.html>, accessed on 01 Sep 2024

⁴⁰ Tech Target, Semiconductor, available at: <https://www.techtarget.com/whatis/definition/semiconductor#:~:text=It%20controls%20and%20manages%20the,%2C%20including%20solid%2Dstate%20storage>, accessed on 4 April 2024

⁴¹ World Population Review, Semiconductor Manufacturing by Country 2024, available at: <https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/semiconductor-manufacturing-by-country>, accessed on 07 April 2024

⁴² <https://www.deccanherald.com/world/political-unrest-worldwide-is-fueled-by-high-prices-and-huge-debts-3093623>, accessed on 02 Aug 2024

⁴³ <https://www.un.org/en/un75/new-era-conflict-and-violence>, accessed on 02 Aug 2024

⁴⁴ <https://geneva-academy.ch/galleries/today-s-armed-conflicts>, accessed on 02 Aug 2024

⁴⁵ Merriam-webster, (2024), recidivism, available at: <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/recidivism>, accessed on 5 March 2024

⁴⁶ Says Rab (2024), A drivers' gang behind abduction of university student, Jan 26, available at: <https://www.thedailystar.net/news/bangladesh/crime-justice/news/drivers-gang-behind-abduction-univ-student-3528481>, accessed on April 10, 2024

⁴⁷ Somoy tv (2024), এ কেমন আপসোস! খুনের জন্য আপসোস! [instagram], Feb 23, available at:

another incident, a man who had been jailed for murdering 4 members of a family after which he killed 3 more members of the same family while out in bail.⁴⁸ These re-offenders are the reason why the recidivism rate is so high. There isn't much research done on recidivism in Bangladesh. People in general are not aware of the concept let alone the word. It is very hard to come by an article or news about this topic. The eastern nations have a very hard time keeping track or tabs on such topics as not enough research or effort is put on these subjects. Universities and research centers should put more effort and emphasis on these points of research. Not enough journalists are shading light on this topic. The people has the right to know why the crime rates are so high, only after that people would vote people into office to deal with these problems. In a democracy until and unless people are aware of a problem they can't advocate for it and vote the right people into office to collect data and act adoringly to it to actively improve the situation.

Rate of Recidivism and Growing Economies Facing Crisis

According to a recent report, the recidivism rate of prisoners was in 77.7% in the year of 2017 in Bangladesh and that is the highest ever been.⁴⁹ This is a very high rate of recidivism rate that can actively harm the people's trust in the legal system. If mass criminals can't be constrained or stopped from committing crime then people will start to question the legal system. The one of the works of the justice system is to take away the burden of punishing the wrong doer, freeing the person who has been wronged.⁵⁰ So if the people think that the justice system is not able to deliver justice and keep people safe; then general mass might take justice in their own hands causing more injustice is going to take place. Therefore, it is going to create a cycle of injustice and which will put more pressure on

the exhausted and stretched legal system in addition. That is why, recidivism plays an vital role of the criminal justice system. It seems that since 2010 and beyond the recidivism rate has been above 70%.⁵¹ It looks like a terrible trend for Bangladesh's recidivism rate.

The most of the other nations in the Asian continent are not doing that well either. In 2021 Pakistan had a recidivism rate of around 70% as well.⁵² Technologically advanced and a forward thinking nation like Japan has a recidivism rate of 47.9% in 2022.⁵³ The report goes as far as to report that almost half of the prison inmates in Japan are re-offenders.⁵⁴ It is not like eastern nations have fallen behind in regards of stopping re-offenders the west has to deal with its own problems too. Germany is one of the leading economies in Europe and has to contribute 2% of its GDP to defense for the first time since the 90s in 2022.⁵⁵ Germany still has a re-conviction rate of 48% and a 35% re-imprisonment rate.⁵⁶ The UK had a recidivism rate of 24.9% as of 2022.⁵⁷

One of the UN report forecasts a deceleration in global GDP growth, from an estimated 2.7% in 2023 to 2.4% in 2024, which signaling a continuation of lethargic growth trends. However, developing economies, in particular, are struggling to recover from pandemic-induced losses, with many facing high debt and investment shortfalls.⁵⁸ It is true for Bangladesh as well. The United States of America (USA) is the world's richest and second biggest economy after China in terms of GDP. It has the world's biggest military as it spends half if it's annual beget on military spending. The US police are one of the most heavily militarized police force seen during a peace time in any single country in the world as they have increasingly acquired military-grade weaponry, equipment and

https://www.instagram.com/reel/C3uPKikP3YG/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==, Somoy tv, 2024, 0.21, accessed on April 10, 2024

⁴⁸ Ibid

⁴⁹ Nelufer Yesmen (2022), 'Recidivism of Prisoners in Bangladesh: Trends and Causes', Feb 23, available at: [file:///D:/LLB%20\(Hons\)/uni%20competitions/Juvinile%20Crime%20repeat%20rate%20in%20Bangladesh/source/recidivism%20rate%20of%20bangladesh.pdf](file:///D:/LLB%20(Hons)/uni%20competitions/Juvinile%20Crime%20repeat%20rate%20in%20Bangladesh/source/recidivism%20rate%20of%20bangladesh.pdf), accessed on April 13, 2024

⁵⁰ Jordan B Peterson (2017), 2017 Maps of Meaning 11: The Flood and the Tower, May 18. Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T4fjSrVCDvA&t=0s>, Jordan B Peterson, 2017, 01.23.53, accessed on April 13, 2024

⁵¹ Opcit, Nelufer Yesmen (2022)

⁵² Abdullah Ahmad (2021), The best way to reform Pakistan's criminal justice system, April 30, available at: <https://www.globalvillagespace.com/the-best-way-to-reform-pakistans-criminal-justice-system/#:~:text=Unfortunately%2C%20as%20a%20result%20of,Pakistan%20would%20be%20approximately%20around,accessed%20on%20April%2015,%202024>

⁵³ Nippon (2023), Annual Crime Figures in Japan Rise for First Time in 20 Years, Dec 28. Available at: <https://www.nippon.com/en/japan-data/h01860/#:~:text=The%20total%20number%20of%20ar>

[rests,two%20consecutive%20years%20since%202021,accessed on April 15, 2024](rests,two%20consecutive%20years%20since%202021,accessed%20on%20April%2015,%202024)

⁵⁴ Ibid

⁵⁵ Reuters (2024), Germany hits 2% NATO spending target for first time since end of Cold War, Feb 14, available at: [https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/germany-hits-2-nato-target-first-time-since-1992-reports-dpa-2024-02-14/#:~:text=BERLIN%2C%20Feb%2014%20\(Reuters\),invasion%20of%20Ukraine%20in%202022,accessed on April 15, 2024](https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/germany-hits-2-nato-target-first-time-since-1992-reports-dpa-2024-02-14/#:~:text=BERLIN%2C%20Feb%2014%20(Reuters),invasion%20of%20Ukraine%20in%202022,accessed%20on%20April%2015,%202024)

⁵⁶ FAIR AND JUST PROSECUTION (2024), Lessons Learned from Germany: Avoiding Unnecessary Incarceration and Limiting Collateral Consequences, (no date). Available at: https://fairandjustprosecution.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/FJP_Brief_GermanIncarceration.pdf, accessed on April 15, 2024

⁵⁷ Statista (2024), Proportion of offenders who re-offend in England and Wales from 2008/09 to 2021/22, 3 July, Available at: [https://www.statista.com/statistics/317299/re-offending-in-england-and-wales/#:~:text=In%202021%2F22%2C%2024.9%20percent,24%20percent%20in%202020%2F21,accessed on April 15, 2024](https://www.statista.com/statistics/317299/re-offending-in-england-and-wales/#:~:text=In%202021%2F22%2C%2024.9%20percent,24%20percent%20in%202020%2F21,accessed%20on%20April%2015,%202024)

⁵⁸

<https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/blog/2024/01/overview-world-economic-situation-and-prospects-2024/>, accessed on 02 Aug 2024

personal armor ever since 9/11.⁵⁹ The USA has a recidivism rate of 44% and these ex-convicts return within the first 1 year of release.⁶⁰ The State of Alaska of USA has been identified by multiple articles with the highest recidivism rate of any place. As of 2019 the USA has 70% recidivism rate within 5 year period.⁶¹

World's Lowest Recidivism Rate Nation

Prosperity and happiness is much more than money and assets, it is about growth, opportunity, freedom and responsibility. History reveals the foundations of prosperity and that tell us it encompasses beliefs, ethics, values, culture and traditions and which create virtuous people, trust-based societies, powerful countries and strong nations.⁶² Most research articles and well circulated news explain that Scandinavian countries are the most prosperous and fast nations in the world. In fact The Legatum Prosperity Index (LPI) has consistently ranked Norway, Sweden, and Denmark as the top 3 most prosperous nations in the world where as Bangladesh ranks as 124 in 2023 with comparison.⁶³ Norway, as one of the world's lowest recidivism rate,⁶⁴ is having recidivism rate of just 20% in a period of 5 years.⁶⁵ The capital city of Norway, Oslo is known as one of the safest cities in the world. Oslo has a safety rate of 66.5 putting it at 94th place in compared to capital city of Bangladesh Dhaka

getting 37.5 putting it as 292th place in the list.⁶⁶ In the 1980s the recidivism rate of Norway was 60% to 70%,⁶⁷ and they managed to bring it down to 20% within just a couple of decades.

The Norwegian Justice system focuses more on rehabilitating its convicts more than punishing them. They started to rework their justice system since the 1960s to actively address their issues with the high re-offending rate and by 1975 the juvenile delinquency centers were abolished.⁶⁸ Norway is has a justice system that is called as a "Rehabilitative Justice System" where as Bangladesh has a justice system that is known as a "Punitive Justice System", and this approach to justice makes Norway different from other criminal justice systems. The result of this is that Norway has a much lower recidivism rate than the other countries. It has been found that, an ongoing deterioration in Political Accountability and Freedom of Speech and Assembly in most regions of the world.⁶⁹ A color coded map of world showing the prosperity of countries according to the Legatum Prosperity Index published in 2023 has been displayed in figure 3 below. A detailed Robinson projection SVG map shaded by country using a distributed red and green palette according to the World Happiness Report (WHR)⁷⁰ score in 2023 has been shown in figure 4 below.

Figure 3: A color coded global map showing the prosperity of countries according to LPI in 2023⁷¹

⁵⁹ America Police Beat (2023), The use of military assets by U.S. police, Oct 22, available at: <https://apbweb.com/2023/10/the-use-of-military-assets-by-u-s-police/>, accessed on April 16, 2024

⁶⁰ Wisevoter (2024), Recidivism Rate by State, Available at: <https://wisevoter.com/state-rankings/recidivism-rates-by-state/#:~:text=Recidivism%20rates%20in%20the%20U.S.,within%20their%20first%20year%20out>, accessed on April 16, 2024

⁶¹ Madalyn Hayden (2023), Recidivism Rates in the United States versus Europe: How and Why are they Different?, April 18, available at: https://scholarworks.wmich.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=4677&context=honors_theses#:~:text=Recidivism%20rate%20are%20a%20good,of%20prisoners%20will%20have%20reoffended, accessed on April 16, 2024

⁶² <https://www.prosperity.com/>, accessed on 02 Aug 2024

⁶³ The Legatum Prosperity Index (2023), The 2023 Legatum Prosperity Overview Report, available at: [file:///D:/LLB%20\(Hons\)/uni%20competitions/Juvenile%20Crime%20repeat%20rate%20in%20Bangladesh/source/The_2023_Legatum_Prosperty_Overview_report.pdf](file:///D:/LLB%20(Hons)/uni%20competitions/Juvenile%20Crime%20repeat%20rate%20in%20Bangladesh/source/The_2023_Legatum_Prosperty_Overview_report.pdf), accessed on April 16, 2024

⁶⁴ Wikipedia, Recidivism, available at: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Recidivism#:~:text=Norway%20has%20one%20of%20the,rehabilitating%20prisoners%20rather%20than%20punishment>, accessed on April 16, 2024

⁶⁵ Opcit, Madalyn Hayden (2023)

⁶⁶ Numbeo (2024), Current Safety Index by City, available at: https://www.numbeo.com/crime/rankings_current.jsp?displayColumn=1, accessed on April 16, 2024)

⁶⁷ Wikipedia, Incarceration in Norway, available at: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Incarceration_in_Norway#:~:text=In%201975%2C%20juvenile%20delinquency%20centers,focused%20much%20more%20on%20rehabilitation, accessed on April 16, 2024

⁶⁸ Ibid

⁶⁹ <https://www.legatum.com/news/article/2023-legatum-prosperity-index-launches/>, accessed on 02 Aug 2024

⁷⁰ World Happiness Report - Wikipedia, accessed on 02 Aug 2024

⁷¹ https://www.reddit.com/r/MapPorn/comments/129tes5/oc_overall_prosperity_level_according_to_the/?rdt=36350, accessed on 02 Aug 2024

Figure 4: Global map shaded by distributed red and green according to WHR in 2023⁷²

Different Types of Criminal Justice Systems and Bangladesh Perspective

There are different types of criminal justice systems that aim to deal with crime and criminals in a different approach. The work of a criminal justice system is to control crime and criminal activities, punish the offenders, prevent crimes, protect the innocent, and to maintain stability in a country. There are 3 main types of criminal justice systems that have a unique approach to counter crime and criminal activities. They are: Restorative Justice System, Rehabilitative Justice System, and Punitive Justice System.

a. Restorative justice System. Restorative justice is where the justice system is structured to “restore” the victim to their previous position to a state before the victim suffered from the actions of the criminal. It is about restoring both the victim and the wrongdoer to their pre-criminal act stage what is known

as the 5 ‘R’s: Relationship, Respect, Responsibility, Repair, and Reintegration.⁷³ Some legal scholars think that “Blood money” which is the penalty money paid by the offender as compensation to the victim or his family,⁷⁴ is a form of Restorative Justice. Things like Blood money is usually used to pay for violent crimes like murder, while things like community service could be sentenced for lesser crimes like assault or money laundering and for things like theft the return of the stolen item and payment of damages for harm to property can be used. The argument is that if an offender is put behind bars still don’t return the victim the things they have lost in addition to the offender no longer being able to contribute to the community. So it aims to restore the victim to their previous state while making the criminal work to actively rectify and repay for this or her actions back to the victim along with the community.

⁷²https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:World_map_of_countries_by_World_Happiness_Report_score_%282023%29.svg, accessed on 02 Aug 2024

⁷³ Restorative Solutions (2024), The 5 ‘R’s of Restorative Justice: Are They Always Applicable?, available at: <https://www.restorativesolutions.org.uk/news/the-5-r-s-of-restorative-justice-are-they-always-applicable>, accessed on 24 May, 2024

⁷⁴ Wikipedia, Blood money (restitution), available at: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Blood_money_\(restitution\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Blood_money_(restitution)), accessed on 24 May, 2024

Figure 4: Minimum monthly pay of RMG worker in 2023 and chronological development⁷⁵

The offender if kept in lockup cannot contribute to the economy either. In 2022 Bangladesh the work force employment by job sector was 36.86% of the employees were in the agricultural sector, 21.88% in industry and 41.26% in the service sector.⁷⁶ The government has published the gazette on the recently declared minimum wage for readymade garment (RMG) workers, setting the monthly pay at Tk 12,500 in 2023⁷⁷ and which has been shown in figure 5 above. This means that majority of the work-force of Bangladesh are labor or workers. Their average salary is around TK 26000 per month where as the minimum wage is approximately TK 5290 per month (in remote area and extreme cases with some exception).⁷⁸ These workers have families and children of their own. When someone is put in prison due to any crime, they cannot even earn this money, let alone contribute to the economy. It is the bare minimum of what kind of economic exchange that is taken out of the economy. Children from these families are left without a parent or both parents who can earn and look after them which might further force them to choose a life of crime as well just to survive.

Restorative Justice is not perfect. There are offenders like serial killers, serial arsonist and homicidal maniacs who can't function in a regular society and these people cannot contribute to society in a meaningful way. These "serial offenders" are people who have been convicted of doing the same crime or a series of crimes again and again,⁷⁹ might abuse this system. Their minds don't work like normal people's minds. They might see it as a legal fee that they have to pay for committing the crime, which is not the intention of Restorative Justice. It is also important to understand that things like Blood money is paid as reparation of their criminal deeds and if accepted there can be no personal vengeance taken by the victim or his family. One of the works of the Criminal justice System is to elevate the need for personal vengeance,⁸⁰ and this might not what the victim or his family wants and they might not think it's appropriate or think it's enough to just get monetarily compensated. In a recent case, where a girl getting violently raped to death by 5 men and a juvenile delinquent in a moving bus⁸¹, her family might not want their daughter's pain and suffering to be waves by money and they might think that the offenders

⁷⁵ <https://www.thedailystar.net/business/news/govt-publishes-gazette-new-rmg-wage-3468181>, accessed on 02 Aug 2024

⁷⁶ Statista (2024), Bangladesh: Distribution of employment by economic sector from 2012 to 2022, (Jan 14), available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/438360/employment-by-economic-sector-in-bangladesh/#:~:text=In%202022%2C%2036.86%20percent%20of,percent%20in%20the%20service%20sector>, 24 May, 2024

⁷⁷ Bangladesh garment workers minimum salary Tk 12500 | Tk 12,500 declared as minimum RMG wage (thedailystar.net), accessed on 02 Aug 2024

⁷⁸ Time Champ (2024), AVERAGE SALARY IN BANGLADESH, available at: [https://www.timechamp.io/blogs/average-salary-in-bangladesh/#:~:text=also%20Look%20For%3A-,What%20is%20The%20Average%20Salary%20in%20Bangladesh%3F,\(237.63%20USD\)%20per%20month](https://www.timechamp.io/blogs/average-salary-in-bangladesh/#:~:text=also%20Look%20For%3A-,What%20is%20The%20Average%20Salary%20in%20Bangladesh%3F,(237.63%20USD)%20per%20month), accessed on 24 May, 2024

⁷⁹ Law Insider (2024), Relevant serial offender definition, available at: <https://www.lawinsider.com/dictionary/relevant-serial-offender/#:~:text=relevant%20serial%20offender%20means%20a,Based%20on%2013%20documents>, accessed on 24 May, 2024

⁸⁰ Opcit, Jordan B Peterson (2017)

⁸¹ Aljazeera (2020), Timeline: Delhi gang rape and murder case, (20 Mar 2020), available at: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2020/3/20/timeline-delhi-gang-rape-and-murder->

cover faster. In Norway prisoners are treated as human beings brought in to rectify their mistakes not to pay with their lives and relationships for it.

However Norway system wouldn't work well in Bangladesh and is also not possible to effort. This system of rehabilitating offenders would only work if the main root of the problem is solved. In most cases criminals do crime for economic reasons or to improve their current economic condition. In Bangladesh most people are engaged unskilled or semi skilled work for very little pay. It is only in recent times that Bangladesh has achieved the status of a lower-middle income country.⁹³ The average household income in Bangladesh is TK 32,422 per month in 2022 where as the household spending is TK 31,500 in 2022. This means that they have very little when it comes to saving.⁹⁴ The national average of literacy rate is 74% though it is important to note that the urban places have a bit higher literacy rate than the national average while the rural areas are a bit behind on that matter compared to the national average.⁹⁵ A huge number of people are also living in relative poverty as well and some of them are living even below poverty. In cities like Dhaka slums has considered as a huge problem. Moreover, It has been found that, many homeless people doing drugs business and taking drugs on the streets. Actually, if people can't make a living earning of their jobs then they can be highly be susceptible to crime and criminal behavior.

c. Punitive System. Punitive system is a criminal justice system that aims to punish offenders for their actions. Example of a punitive system is Bangladesh and the USA. Most of the nations with this kind of criminal justice system have longer and harsher prison sentence along with death penalty for the most violent crimes like murder. There are 55 countries that still have the death penalty as a part of their criminal justice system and in 2022 alone there have been almost 2000 execution.⁹⁶ It is one of the oldest criminal justice systems in the old. The idea of punishing someone for their crimes is one oldest form of criminal justice there is. It can take many forms, from leaving the glutinous member of the tribe who refuses to contribute and eat others food behind during ancient times to being given death sentence by poison needle in today in some nations including the US. A punitive system produces an instant result and it is for the people to see the consequences of their criminal behaviors. It lets people know that their criminal behaviors are not encouraged

nor will they be tolerated. It produces a more tangible and easily understandable outcome of a criminal behavior. It does directly deter criminal behaviors as the people especially young people can see the consequences of engaging in criminal behavior.

However it is not without its flaws. In South-East Asian countries like Bangladesh the main bread winner of the family is a single parent usually the father. It is statically found that more men do cause crime in Bangladesh and are kept in prison as such,⁹⁷ so if they are put to prison, from there they cannot help their families anymore. It becomes harder to properly be a present parent with their kids while bring the sole bread winner for the family as well, as a direct result of one of the parental figures goes to prison. This might force the mother to take some less then ethical ways to make money.

It is found that children with single parents are more likely to become involved with crime even more so if they are left with a single mother.⁹⁸ A child needs the attention of both a loving and caring mother and a protective and inspiring father in their lives. When a father goes to prison the mother is left to not only handle her role as a mother but to handle the role of the father as well. Things take a turn for the worst when they are not able to maintain their marriage and decide to get divorce after the father figure has been put behind bars. There isn't enough social support system for single mothers and society pushes them to get remarried soon as well.⁹⁹ There is no replacement for the father figure in someone's life and this is no exception when it comes to children. Children know and can feel that something or someone important is missing from their lives or is being replaced. It is commonly seen that children are not very accepting of a step parent. Children in "blended families" or step families don't do very well emotionally, academically or socially.¹⁰⁰ A child of divorce may feel grief or loss of their beloved parental figure and see their step father as trying to replace their father's love which just might be a simple change in parenting style. These children grow up with a resentful and bitter world view. They might act out to seek emotional attention. Children in such conditions may grow up with communication issues, be more stressed and have issues trusting people and forming deep and long lasting emotional attachments, which might hamper them in their future relationships.¹⁰¹

⁹³ Daily Star (2024), Bangladesh has capacity to become upper middle income country by 2031: ICCB, available at: <https://www.thedailystar.net/news/bangladesh/development/news/bangladesh-has-capacity-become-upper-middle-income-country-2031-iccb-3585001>, accessed on 11 June, 2024

⁹⁴ Bangladesh Gov portal (2022), Household income and expenditure survey HIES 2022, available at: https://bbs.portal.gov.bd/sites/default/files/files/bbs.portal.gov.bd/page/57def76a_aa3c_46e3_9f80_53732eb94a83/2023-04-13-09-35-ee41d2a35dcc47a94a595c88328458f4.pdf, accessed on 11 June, 2024

⁹⁵ Ibid

⁹⁶ BBC News World (2024), How many countries still have the death penalty, and how many people are executed?, 25

January, available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-45835584>, accessed on 11 June, 2024

⁹⁷ Opcit, World Prison Brief data (2024)

⁹⁸ Vrije Universiteit (2024), Amsterdam Criminal behaviour and growing up in single-parent household, available at: <https://vu.nl/en/research/criminal-behaviour-and-growing-up-in-single-parent-household>, accessed on 15 June, 2024

⁹⁹ Bibaha bd (2024), Single Mother in Bangladesh, available at: <https://bibahabd.net/web/3982>, accessed on 15 June, 2024

¹⁰⁰ WebMd (2024), What is blended family, available at: <https://www.webmd.com/parenting/what-is-a-blended-family>, accessed on 15 June, 2024

¹⁰¹ Psychology Today (2023), Are Kids More Likely to Divorce if Their Parents Did?, Aug 13, available at: <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/a-better->

This is more so visible in teenagers in blended families. They might become more emotionally avoidant and try to do drugs or other types of substance abuse to avoid their negative feelings. There is a statically a higher chance of such young people doing substance abuse than their peers who has both parental figure.¹⁰² They might involve themselves in violent crime to fuel their drug abuse. Mobile or chain snatchers in big highways in Bangladesh are done mainly young by people or teenagers who sometimes use sharp objects to strike their victims on buses and Lorries to snatch their belongings and make a run for it.¹⁰³ These are organized crime rings that these young people are getting themselves involved in. The DB says that there are 300 mobile phones are snatched every day as of 2023 and over 20 places have been identified as hot spots for these kinds of criminal activities in Dhaka city and nearby areas.¹⁰⁴ The phones distributed according to their value as cheap phones could be sold directly on the local black market where as the more expensive phones are sold for parts rather than in one piece,¹⁰⁵ as their owner are likely to try to find their devices.

This just goes to show that putting even a single parent in the prison system can break or even push the entire family closer to that same cell. Then there is a question of does the prison system even work as it is intended to do so. Putting all criminals in one place surrounded by walls, where they have no normal or non criminal people to talk to, and only other criminals to socially engage with is not very smart. The prison system is still stuck in the 19th century design philosophy trying to hold 21st century prisoners.¹⁰⁶ There are criminals who learn how to steal luxury cars on their first day in prison.¹⁰⁷ Prison is where white collar criminals learn from blue collar criminals and cooks teach each other how to create and sell more powerful and addictive drugs, learn how to cook meth, etc.¹⁰⁸ This is specially a big concern if young people are put into the same prison system.¹⁰⁹ They will get involved into more violent crimes and gang wars. To them this will become the natural way of life, which is

scary as they will have a higher chance of becoming a sociopath.

Conclusion

It has been observed that some of the most acute and omnipresent human rights abuses take place in times of war, crisis and conflict around the world. Interestingly, like a globe-spanning tornado that touches down with little unavoidability, deep economic anxieties are leaving a trail of political turmoil and violence across poor and rich countries alike. Again, in 2022, the cost-of-living protests occurred in 122 countries and territories, with an estimated 3 million person-days dedicated to such demonstrations. And such protests focusing on government energy policies are among the major factors driving cost of living unrest on a global scale. Surprise to us that, richer nations are experiencing a trend of increasing property damage and business interruption as a result of social unrest, and which indicating that this pattern is likely to continue in coming days ahead. So, on going global financial crisis and conflict will worsen more the economic situation of the developing countries; where Bangladesh is not different. As a result crime and criminal activities of young people of developing countries with huge population may grow further as well. By understanding what has worked before, we can considerably apply ancient wisdom to modern challenges, translating sound doctrine and principles into better institutions and policies.

Bangladesh is a country that uses punitive justice system to deal with criminals. We cannot expect the entire criminal justice system to change to a rehabilitant justice system over night. It is expensive, time consuming and might not work for many developing countries like Bangladesh. There are cultural, social and biggest of all economic differences between Bangladesh and develop country Norway. What we can try to do is improve the situation for young offenders. There are over 1.6 million children who live in the streets in Bangladesh.¹¹⁰ These children would be easy pickings for criminal gangs to be used for their illegal activities. It might not be the best way to deal with the growing number of Juvenile delinquents. These young

divorce/202306/are-your-children-more-likely-to-divorce-if-you

divorce#:~:text=Children%20growing%20up%20in%20a,dynamics%2C%20or%20poor%20communication%20skills, accessed on 26 June, 2024

¹⁰² Stonewater Recovery (2024), How Divorce Affects Your Teen's Substance Abuse, available at: <https://www.stonewaterrecovery.com/adolescent-treatment-blog/how-divorce-affects-your-teens-substance-abuse#:~:text=Statistics%20show%20that%20teenagers%20whose,whose%20parents%20have%20remained%20together,> accessed on 26 June, 2024

¹⁰³ Somoy tv (2024), সড়কে নিরাপত্তা ফিরবে কবে?, July 1, available at: https://www.instagram.com/reel/C832J0ui0ZI/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==, accessed on 26 June, 2024

¹⁰⁴ Newsagebd (2023), 300 cell phones snatched in Dhaka daily: DB. February 4, available at: <https://www.newagebd.net/article/193544/300-cell-phones-snatched-in-dhaka-daily-db>, accessed on 1 July, 2024

¹⁰⁵ Ibid

¹⁰⁶ Richard Garside (2021), A 19th century solution to a 21st century problem, May 28, available at: <https://www.crimeandjustice.org.uk/resources/19th-century-solution-21st-century-problem>, accessed on 1 July, 2024

¹⁰⁷ The Guardian (2015), The current prison system is a 19th-century approach to tackling crime, It needn't be this way, December 21, available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2015/dec/21/c-an-prison-work-crime>, accessed on 2 July 2024

¹⁰⁸ Prison writers, James Wallace (2024), PRISON IS A SCHOOL FOR CRIMINALS, available at: <https://prisonwriters.com/in-prison-we-learn-how-to-be-better-criminals>, 2 July 2024

¹⁰⁹ University of Rochester Medical Center (2024), Understanding the Teen Brain, available at: <https://www.urmc.rochester.edu/encyclopedia/content.aspx?ContentTypeID=1&ContentID=3051#:~:text=The%20rational%20part%20of%20a,cortex%2C%20the%20brain's%20rational%20part,> accessed on 2 July 2024

¹¹⁰ The Daily star (2024) Nobody's children, available at: <https://www.thedailystar.net/news/bangladesh/news/nobodys-children-3232366>, accessed on 2 July 2024

people have their entire lives ahead of them to learn and correct their mistakes, labeling them as criminals for the rest of their lives is going to further alienate them; and the push them closer to a permanent life of crime. The human brain grows and continues to develop until the age of 25, so a young offender still has some time to change and improve themselves. Instead of punishing, by putting them in the same prison system where there are rapists, murderers and drug kingpins, we can help them to become better, useful, quality and independent citizens. A child or young lost is not just a

simple statistic rather it's a nation losing one of its potential champions. As young people are driving changes towards a better future for us in every corner of the world. They are leading global action on climate change, campaigning to end discrimination, speaking out to uphold democracy and the freedom of speech, connecting our world with innovations in advanced smart technology, and building peace in societies, nations around the globe. And same ideas and goals remain valid for any developing countries like Bangladesh.